

INFLUENCE FACTORS ON FATIGUE STRENGTH OF ARC-WELDED JOINTS USING ULTRA-HIGH STRENGTH STEEL SHEETS AND ITS IMPROVING METHODS

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The fatigue strength of arc welded joints with ultra-high strength steel (UHSS) is known to be low, yet the underlying cause remains elusive. This study aims to elucidate the effect of base metal strength and stress concentration on the fatigue strength of these joints, employing a fracture mechanics approach. Experimentally, we examined arc welded joints with mechanically ground toe radii ranging from 0.5 mm to 1.5 mm, using two types of steel with tensile strengths of 440 MPa and 980 MPa. Our findings indicate that the fatigue strength of mechanically ground joints improved drastically when UHSS was used, and this improvement was accurately predicted. However, this was not the case for as-welded joints. The study suggests that this discrepancy may be attributed to the microstructural effect. Lastly, we compared several methods for enhancing fatigue strength, finding that significant improvements were achieved by altering the residual stress and microstructure, without the need to reduce stress concentration.

Keywords: Ultra-high strength steel, Fatigue, arc-welded joint, life prediction

INTRODUCTION

Battery electric vehicles (BEVs) are spreading rapidly. Since the heavy batteries increase load on chassis components, ultra-high strength steel (UHSS), i.e., steel with the tensile strength more than 980 MPa, is getting attention. In addition, use of UHSS improve energy efficiency by reducing weight regardless of the power source of vehicles. There is, therefore, an interest in applying UHSS to chassis parts (Schmitt and Jung [1], Funakawa and Nagataki [2] Yamaguchi et al. [3]). However, it is well known that the fatigue strength of as-welded steel joints does not increase with the yield or tensile strength of the steel (Kitani et al. [4], Yamaguchi et al. [5]). Therefore, in order to reduce the thickness of the parts, it is necessary to improve the fatigue strength of the welded joints. To develop fatigue improving methods, influence factors on fatigue strength on the UHSS joint should be clarified.

Fatigue fracture of arc-welded joints occurs frequently at the weld toe [4,5]. The fatigue strength are affected by stress concentration (Shiozaki et al. [6], Shen et al. [7], Matsuda and Kodama [8],

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Alam et al. [9] and Schork et al. [10].), residual stress (Soyama [11], James et al. [12], Zhang et al. [13], Cui et al. [14].) and the microstructure (Nishikawa et al. [16], Yamaguchi et al. [17], Okuda et al. [18], Sedmak et al. [19] and Liu et al. [20].) of the toe. Although many prediction methods were proposed (Toyosada et al. [21-24], Zerbst et al. [25], Kang, G., and Luo [26]), few study investigated UHSS sheet joints.

The authors previously demonstrated [6] that weld toe machining by a ball endmill significantly improved the fatigue strength of welded joints of an UHSS sheet with tensile strength grade of 980 MPa, where the toe radius was 0.5 mm. Besides, the effect of base material's strength on the improvement of the toe-machining is still unclear. Knight [27] showed that the fatigue strength improvement for a high strength steel was significantly higher than that for a mild steel. However, Pedersen et al. [28], Vosikovskiy [29] found that the improvement in fatigue strength is independent of the tensile strength of the steel. It is well-known that the notch factor, the ratio of the fatigue strength between smooth to notched specimens, increases with the strength (Yao et al. [30]). Still, authors' other study [18] with surface notch sheet showed that the notch factor depends on the microstructure.

In addition, the authors also reported [6] that fatigue life prediction based on fracture mechanics showed good agreement with experiments on toe machined joints with various toe radii. On the other hand, the prediction overestimated the fatigue life and the fatigue limit of the as-welded joint, especially in the high-cycle region. This result seems to be related to the reason why the fatigue strength of as-welded steel joints does not increase with the strength of the base metal.

The purpose of the present study is to verify the toe-machining effect on 440 MPa grade joints, which are commonly used in practice and to clarify the influence factors on the fatigue strength of arc-welded joints using a UHSS sheet by comparing 980 MPa and 440 MPa grade joints. Finally, we compare the improvement methods against UHSS and consider how the governing factors act.

METHODOLOGY

Material and specimens

The materials used in this study were two kinds of hot-rolled steel sheets with tensile strength grades of 440 MPa and 980 MPa. The thickness of both steels was 2.9 mm. The welding wire was a 1.2 mm diameter welding wire of 780 MPa grade named MG-S80 manufactured by Kobe steel. Ltd. The chemical compositions and the mechanical properties and the welding condition are shown in TABLE 1 and TABLE 2, respectively. While the yield strength of the 440MPa-grade steel was the upper yield point, that of the 980MPa-grade steel was the 0.2% proof stress. The fatigue test specimens of the steel sheets were prepared referring to [6]. Lap fillet welded joints were manufactured with the welding condition shown in TABLE 3. The geometry of the fatigue test specimens is shown in FIGURE 1. The weld toes of the specimens were machined with three kinds of ball endmills with the tool tip radii of 0.5 mm, 1.0 mm, and 1.5 mm, respectively. The surface was electro-polished to remove the effect of work hardening. The cross-sections around the weld toes of the as-welded joint and the toe machined joints are shown in FIGURE 2. The depth of the machined groove was 0.15 mm in all the machined joints.

The weld toe geometries of the as-welded specimens were measured with a non-contact 3D measurement system (Keyence VR-3100) to create finite element analysis models. Two of the 440 MPa grade steel joint specimens were measured and 15 to 16 transverse cross-sections per specimen

were measured. The hardness on the transverse cross-section of the as-welded joint was measured with a Vickers hardness testing machine. The position of the hardness measurement was 0.1 mm from the surface. The testing load for the measurement was 0.98 N. The cross-section was etched with a picral solution to reveal the microstructure of the welded joint.

TABLE 1 Chemical compositions

Steels	C	Si	Mn	P	S	Others	Fe
440MPa-grade	0.06	0.02	1.35	0.01	0.001	-	Balance
980MPa-grade	0.06	0.71	1.80	0.01	0.001	Cr, Ti, B	Balance
MG-S80	0.05	0.51	1.37	0.01	0.002	Ni, Cr, Mo, Cu	Balance

TABLE 2 Mechanical properties

Steels	Yield strength (MPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elongation (%)
440MPa-grade	859	997	13
980MPa-grade	388	453	16

TABLE 3 Welding condition

Current (A)	Voltage (V)	Speed (MPa)	Gas	Gas flow rate (L/min)
200	20	1.0	Ar-20%CO ₂	20

FIGURE 1 Geometry of specimen.

FIGURE 2 Cross-sections around weld toes of 440 MPa grade (a) as-welded joint and (b)-(d) toe machined welded joints with toe radius r of (b) 0.5 mm, (c) 1.0 mm, (d) 1.5 mm.

Fatigue tests

Four-point plane bending fatigue tests were conducted in servo-hydraulic fatigue testing machines under the stress ratio $R = 0.05$ and frequency of 15 Hz in air at room temperature [6]. The fatigue tests were stopped when the displacement of the actuator heads reached 0.5 mm, or the number of cycles reached 3×10^6 . In order to reveal the fatigue crack propagation process in the welded joints, the beach marks on the fracture surface were produced by two-level low-high block tensile loadings, which were sequentially applied to some specimens.

After the fatigue tests with the beach marks, some specimens after the beach mark testing were cooled in liquid nitrogen and then were broken to measure the development of the aspect ratio of the crack. The nominal stress ranges of the as-welded joint specimens were calculated by the sheet thicknesses and widths of the specimens. That of the toe machined specimens were calculated by the thicknesses at the bottoms of the machined grooves and the widths of the specimens.

Fatigue life prediction

Fatigue life prediction based on a fracture mechanics approach was conducted for the as-welded joints and the toe machined joints, referring to [6]. Since the stress intensity factors of surface cracks in the welded joints are required with this approach, the stress intensity factors were derived from calculations of those for surface cracks in plates subjected to the through-thickness stress distributions obtained in the welded joints [6,21]. The total fatigue life of a welded joint was predicted by calculating a crack initiation life and a crack propagation life. The FEM model was also used to calculate the initiation life. Due to the limitation of the number of pages, it is not possible to describe the details of the calculation method, so refer to the author's previous paper [6].

Two-dimensional elastic finite element analyses for the welded joints were conducted using the commercial software Altair Optistruct 13.0. FIGURE 3 shows the finite element models used for the analyses. Since the average of the actual weld toe radius was 0.26 mm, the model's weld toe radius of 0.2 mm for the as-welded joint shown in FIGURE 3(b) was a slightly severer yet still reasonable because fatigue crack occurred at the weakest point. The finite element models of the machined weld toe joints were prepared by changing the geometry around the weld toe in the as-welded joint model.

Plain strain elements were used for the analyses. Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio were 206 GPa and 0.3, respectively. A bending moment was loaded on both edges in the finite element model.

FIGURE 3 Finite element models of welded joints. (a) Overall view of the model, (b) as-welded joints, (c) toe machined welded joints with radius r of 0.5 mm, (d) toe machined welded joints with radius of 1.0 mm, (e) toe machined welded joints with radius of 1.5 mm [6]

Crack initiation life was calculated referring to the approach based on the effective stress intensity factor range ΔK_{RPG} using a re-tensile plastic zone generated (RPG) load [22]. Crack initiation was defined as the point when a shear crack at a weld toe or a machined groove reached a first grain boundary and the crack opening mode started. Crack initiation life was calculated by Eq. (1).

$$N = \int_0^{r_0} \left\{ C \left(2\lambda\sigma_Y \sqrt{\frac{8}{\eta\pi}} (r_0 + \tilde{\omega}_s - a) \right)^m \right\}^{-1} da \quad (1)$$

The constant m , the plastic constraint factor λ and the proportional constant η were given the values of 2.692, 1.04 and 1.55, respectively, referring to (Hiraide et al. [31]). The constant C was assigned the value of 4.128×10^{-12} , referring to (Zhang and Maddox [32]). The grain size r_0 and the cyclic yield stress σ_Y in Eq. (1) were required in order to predict the crack initiation life. The grain sizes were assumed to be 10 μm and 30 μm based on observation of the microstructure with an optical microscope. The cyclic yield stress at the crack initiation site was estimated using the liner relationship between the cyclic yield stresses and hardness obtained in this study and a reference [31]. FIGURE 4 shows the hardness distributions in as-welded joints of the 440 MPa and 980 MPa grade steels. Since the crack initiation sites were in the vicinity of the fusion lines of the welded joints, the hardness at the fusion lines were employed for the estimation. Those of the 440 MPa and 980 MPa grade steel joints were 194 HV and 300 HV, respectively. FIGURE 5 shows the relationship between the hardness and the cyclic yield stress. The data of the materials used in this study and a reference [31] are included in FIGURE 5, where cyclic yield stresses were obtained from proportional limits of the cyclic stress strain curves. The linear relationship between the hardness and the cyclic yield

stresses was estimated as $\sigma_Y = 1.49HV - 6.54$. Therefore, σ_Y of the 440 MPa and 980 MPa grade joints were estimated as 282 MPa and 440 MPa, respectively.

Crack propagation life was predicted by using the Paris-Erdogan equation shown in Eq. (2).

$$\frac{da}{dN} = A(\Delta K)^{m'} \quad (2)$$

, where $m' = 3.0$ and $A = 1.5 \times 10^{-13}$, respectively. To calculate the stress intensity factor in Eq. (2), the shape of the surface crack in a welded joint was required. Therefore, it was assumed that a half elliptical surface crack existed in a welded joint. The development pattern of the surface crack was fitted as a function of the aspect ratio a/c shown in Eq. (3)

$$\frac{1}{(a/c)^n} = \frac{1}{\{f(x)\}^n} + \frac{1}{\{g(x)\}^n} \quad (3)$$

, where the function was fitted by the experimental data of the beach mark test, referring to [6].

FIGURE 4 Hardness distribution around weld toe.

FIGURE 5 Relationship between hardness and cyclic yield stress.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Fatigue performance

FIGURE 6 shows the fatigue performance of the 440 MPa grade steel joints compared with that of the 980 MPa grade steel joints [6]. As shown in FIGURE 6(a), the fatigue performance of the as-welded joints of the 440 MPa grade steel was similar to that of the 980 MPa grade steel. That is, the fatigue performance of the as-welded joints was independent of the tensile strength of base steel. This result was the same as the result commonly reported. On the other hand, the fatigue strength of the 980 MPa grade steel toe machined joints were considerably higher than that of the 440 MPa grade steel toe machined joints with all machined toe radii, as shown in FIGURE 6(b)-(d). Both the 980 MPa and 440 MPa grade steel joint was improved by the toe machining. However, the improvement in the 440 MPa grade steel joint was much smaller than that in the 980 MPa grade steel joint. With both steels, the improvement in the fatigue strength of the toe machined welded joints against the as-welded joints was almost saturated when the toe radius was larger than 1.0 mm.

FIGURE 6 Comparison of fatigue performances of 440 MPa grade steel welded joints and 980 MPa grade steel welded joints. (a) As-welded joints, (b) toe machined welded joints with toe radius R of 0.5 mm, (c) toe machined welded joints with R of 1.0 mm, (d) toe machined welded joints with R of 1.5 mm. r_0 represents grain size.

DISCUSSION

Comparison of experimental fatigue lives and predicted fatigue lives

The comparison of the experimental fatigue lives and the predicted total fatigue lives is shown in FIGURE 6. The predictions are shown with bands. The upper lines (solid lines) in the bands indicate the predictions under the condition that the grain size r_0 at the notch root was assumed to be 10 μm . The lower lines (dashed lines) in the bands indicate the prediction under the condition that r_0 was assumed to be 30 μm . The predicted total fatigue lives of the as-welded joints of the 980 MPa grade steel were noticeably different from the experimental data in the long fatigue life regime, as shown in FIGURE 6(a). On the other hand, the predicted total fatigue lives of the as-welded joints of the 440 MPa grade steel corresponded to the experimental data, as shown in FIGURE 6(a). Moreover, all the predicted total fatigue lives for the toe machined joints corresponded reasonably well to the experimental data regardless of the steel grade and toe radius, as shown in FIGURE 6(b)-(d).

Validity of fatigue life prediction method for toe machined welded joints and as-welded joints

Since the predicted total fatigue lives for toe machined welded joints reflected the effect of steel strength and were close to the experimental data, as shown in FIGURE 6(b)-(d), it seems that the method of obtaining the total fatigue life from the sum of the calculated crack initiation life and propagation life is appropriate for prediction of the fatigue lives of toe machined welded joints. In the literature [31], it was reported that the fatigue endurance of ground welds can be predicted well by crack growth alone for fatigue endurance of less than 10^6 cycles. However, the experimental data in this study could not be explained well by crack growth alone. This difference can be explained by the quality of the surface. In the literature, the fatigue cracks in a fatigue test propagated from flaws that appeared on or just beneath the ground surface by burr grinding. On the other hand, the weld metals in the weld joints of the 440 MPa and 980 MPa grade steel sheets investigated in this study were sound. Therefore, the prediction method considering crack initiation life and propagation life was considered to be appropriate.

Although the predicted total fatigue lives of the welded joints of the 440 MPa grade steel agreed well with the experimental data, the predictions for the welded joints of the 980 MPa grade steel differed remarkably with the experimental data above 3×10^6 cycles. That is, the prediction method used in this study was not suitable for predictions for as-welded joints. Since the experimental fatigue performance was independent of steel strength, it seems that crack propagation life dominated the fatigue performance of the as-welded joints because the calculation procedure for the crack propagation lives was independent of material strength parameters. However, the experimental data shows a clear knee point in the 980 MPa grade joint that could not be reproduced by this propagation model alone. Therefore, an appropriate method which is also able to predict the experimental fatigue life in the long-life range is desired.

Finally, we focus on the possibility of microstructural effects in the welded zone to explain the lower fatigue strength of the 980 MPa grade steel as-welded joint than expected. The fatigue cracks in the as welded joints initiate at the fusion line or the weld metal [6], while those of the toe machined joints initiate at the heat affected zone (HAZ). The results of author's other studies [17,18] using the same material as in this study demonstrated the fatigue properties of base metal and butt joints with various notch locations with the notch radius $r = 0.2$ mm same as the toe radius in the as-welded joint. These results showed the fatigue strength of the fusion line at 3×10^6 cycles was 25 % lower than that of base metal with approximately the same hardness. Furthermore, it was lower than fine grain heat affected zone (FGHAZ) even though the hardness of the fusion line was lower than that of FGHAZ. Coincidentally, the difference between the experiment and the prediction was also 25%. Therefore, the microstructural effect could explain the low fatigue strength of UHSS welded joints. The effect can be explained as follows. The fatigue crack in the weld metal and the fusion line initiated and propagated along the block boundaries of lath martensite [18]. This result is consistent with several studies (Okada et al. [39], Seidametova et al. [40]) which reported a crack in lath martensite initiated at the block boundaries. As Dai et al. [41] reported cracks within lath grains rather than grain boundaries, there is still controversy about where the crack initiation sites in lath martensite are, which must depend on conditions such as tempering temperature. In addition, the solid-liquid interface at the fusion line may contain contamination, inclusions, or local tensile residual stresses. In any case, the fusion line has low fatigue strength and inevitably exists in the as-welded weld toe, therefore the fatigue strength of the welded joint is govern by that of the fusion line. In conclusion, the difference between the predicted and experimental results for the 980 grade welded joints can be attributed to the low fatigue strength of the fusion line. In other words, the fatigue

strength of the toe machined joint was improved not only by relieving the stress concentration, but also by removing the weld toe and shifting the stress concentration point to FGHAZ. Therefore, a prediction method considering the influence of microstructure is necessary.

Effect of steel grade on fatigue strength of toe machined welded joint

The literature includes two types of results concerning the effect of the steel grade on the fatigue strength improvement by weld toe machining. One type indicates that the fatigue strength improvement effect of a high strength steel is significantly higher than that of a mild steel [27]. The other indicates that the improvement in fatigue strength is independent of the tensile strength of the steel [28, 29]. In this study, the fatigue strength of the toe machined joints improved with increasing tensile strength of the steel with all weld toe machining radii. This result is similar to that in [27]. Although the fatigue strength of the as-welded joints was independent of tensile strength, the fatigue strength improvement obtained by weld toe machining was remarkable in the case of the 980 MPa grade steel. Based on this result, weld toe machining is expected to be a very effective technique for fatigue strength improvement when higher strength grade steel sheets are applied to automobile chassis parts. The improvement in fatigue strength against the as-welded performance were compared with those in references (Watkinson et al. [33], Smith and Hirt [34], Miki et al. [35], Tai and Miki [36]) as shown in TABLE 4. In this table, the improvement is shown by the percentage improvement in fatigue strength at 2×10^6 cycles when compared to the as-welded performance. The improvements in fatigue strength of the transverse and longitudinal non-load-carrying fillet-welded attachments were 105 % in maximum for the steel with yield strength of 685 MPa and approximately 40 % in minimum for the steel with yield strength of below 500 MPa under the treatment condition of only burr grinding. When both burr grinding and polishing treatment were conducted, one result showed improvement of as much as 200 % for the high strength steel with yield strength of 725 MPa. The improvement in fatigue strength for the 980 MPa grade steel joint demonstrated by the authors was 131 %. The result was significantly higher in the case of only grinding treatment.

Furthermore, this study has revealed the effective toe radius for improvement in fatigue strength of welded joints. Comparing FIGURE 6(c) and (d), the increase of fatigue strength in welded joints was slight when the toe radius was over 1.0 mm. If the toe radius is increased further, the throat thickness of the welded joint decreases and the risk of weld root failure can be expected to increase. Therefore, machining of the weld toe should be minimized. The result of this study will provide an appropriate radius for weld toe machining. It has been suggested that the machined toe radius of approximately 1.5 mm leads to sufficient improvement in fatigue strength.

TABLE 4 Percentage improvement in stress range at 2×10^6 cycles for various post-treated joints when compared to their as-welded performance.

Percentage improvement	Yield stress of steel (MPa)	Remarks	Reference (Data source)
(a) Lap fillet welded joints			
33	388	Machined toe radius 0.5mm	This study
57	388	Machined toe radius 1.0mm	This study
57	388	Machined toe radius 1.5mm	This study

62	860	Machined toe radius 0.5mm	[6]
127	860	Machined toe radius 1.0mm	[6]
131	860	Machined toe radius 1.5mm	[6]
(b) Transverse non-load-carrying fillet-welded attachments			
41	<500	Burr grinding	[34] ([27])
75-79	<500	Burr grinding	[34] ([42])
89	406	Burr grinding	[32]
67	431	Burr grinding	[35]
105	685	Burr grinding	[34] ([27])
54-96	<500	Burr grinding and polish	[34] ([42])
82	<500	Burr grinding and polish	[34] ([27])
200	725	Burr grinding and polish	[34] ([33])
(c) Longitudinal non-load-carrying fillet-welded attachments			
13	<500	Burr grinding	[34] ([42])
114	633	Burr grinding	[36]
50-70	<500	Burr grinding and polish	[34] ([42])

Comparison of improving methods

This study pointed that not only stress concentration, which is considered to be the most important, but also microstructure has non-negligible effect on the fatigue strength of an arc-welded joint. In addition, it is well known that residual stress also plays an important role in fatigue strength of welded joints. Although several fatigue improving methods for arc welded joints have been developed, it is important to understand which factor works in each method and how the methods can be improved more.

Micro needle peening (MNP, Yamaguchi et al. [37]) method and the cold spray method (CS, Yamaguchi, et al. [38]) were developed as the fatigue improvement method of the ultra-high strength steel sheet. TABLE 5 shows the methods and influence factors used in each method in comparison with conventional methods, shot peening and needle peening. MNP is a method aimed at obtaining the effect of compressive residual stress and the effect of work hardening the microstructure by striking the weld toe with a pin of a small tip radius instead of obtaining the effect of stress concentration relaxation. In addition, MNP avoids folding defects that ordinary needle peening causes due to a mismatch between the tooltip and toe radii.

FIGURE 7 shows the $S-N$ curves of the 980 MPa grade joint with each method. Toe-machining represents the toe machined 980 joint with the toe radius of 1.5 mm of FIGURE 6 (d). In the above description, the nominal stress is calculated based on the thickness of the groove bottom, but in FIGURE 7, it is calculated based on the thickness of the base metal for comparison with other methods. Among several improving methods, MNP and the shot peening showed the highest improvement. The results show that significant effects can be obtained by changing the residual stress and the microstructure without relaxing the stress concentration. CS forms an iron-alumina

coating on the weld toe, aiming at all the effects of stress relaxation, compressive residual stress, and work hardening. However, the improvement effect of CS is lower than not only MNP and the shot peening but also toe-machining utilizing only stress concentration relaxation. One reason is that the coating contains alumina powder that acts as a defect, and the other reason is that the surface of the coating is rough [38]. In addition, the hardness of the coating was comparable to that of the as-welded weld toe. This indicates that the improvement effect of CS may be even greater if coating technology is improved, and a defect-free hard coating is realized.

TABLE 5 Improving methods and influence factors used.

	Stress concentration relaxation	Residual stress	Work hardening (micro- structural effect)	Negative effect
As-welded [6] [37] [38]	($K_t = 2.49$)	(47 MPa)	(282 HV)	
Shot peening [37]	-	✓ (-391 MPa)	✓ (351HV)	
Micro needle peening [37]	-	✓ (-431 MPa)	✓ (375HV)	
Toe machining [6]	✓ ($K_t = 1.4$)	-	-	
Cold spray [38] (Fe + Al ₂ O ₃ coating)	✓ ($K_t = 1.89$)	✓ (-216 MPa)	✓ (266 HV)	Al ₂ O ₃ in coating, Surface roughness
Needle peening [37]	✓	-326 MPa	✓ (367HV)	Crack-like defect

FIGURE 7 S-N curves of arc-welded joints using 980 MPa grade steel with various improving methods. Nominal stress is calculated based on the thickness of base metal. (Data from [6][37][38])

CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the influence factors on fatigue strength of arc-welded joints using a UHSS sheet by comparing 980 MPa and 440 MPa grade joints. First, the effect of the steel grade on fatigue strength improvement of welded joints with mechanically ground toe radii of 0.5 mm to 1.5 mm by using 440 MPa and 980 MPa grade steels. Second, the fatigue life was predicted based on a fracture mechanics approach, and the appropriateness of this method for predicting the fatigue lives of the as-welded and toe ground welded joints was discussed. Finally, several improvement methods for UHSS welded joints and discuss how the governing factors act. The following conclusions were drawn:

1. The fatigue strength of the toe machined welded joints of the 980 MPa grade steel was considerably higher than that of the toe machined joints of the 440 MPa grade steel.
2. Both the 980 MPa and 440 MPa grade steel joint was improved by the toe machining. However, the improvement in the 440 MPa grade steel joint was much smaller than that in the 980 MPa grade steel joint. With both of these steels, the improvement in the fatigue strength of the toe machined welded joints against the as-welded joints was almost saturated when the toe radius was larger than 1.0 mm.
3. The prediction model well explained the $S-N$ curves of the toe machined welded joints of both 980 MPa and 440 MPa grade steel joints. On the other hand, the prediction for the as-welded joints could not reproduce the experimental data. In particular, especially for 980 joints, the predicted fatigue strength for 980 MPa grade steel joint was 25% higher than the experimental one at 3×10^5 cycles. An appropriate method which is also able to predict the fatigue life of as-welded joints in the long-life range is desired, where microstructural effects should be considered.
4. Among several improving methods, Micro-needle peening (MNP) and shot peening showed the highest improvement, in which both changed the residual stress and the microstructure without relaxing the stress concentration. On the other hand, the improvement effect of a cold spray method was lower than not only MNP and the shot peening but also toe-machining utilizing only stress concentration relaxation. This is due to alumina powder and surface roughness, both of which act as stress concentration sources. This indicates that the improvement effect of CS may be even greater if coating technology is improved, and a defect-free hard coating is realized.

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